

Table 2. Scoring systems for drought resistance at reproductive phase, 12–15 days after start of stress.

Decimal score	Heading ^a	Panicle exertion	Panicle size	Spikelet fertility (%)	Grain filling	Leaf rolling
1	No delay	Full	Normal	91–100	Mostly well-filled	Slight folding
3	Delayed by less than 1 wk	Full	Normal	76–90	Mostly well-filled	Half-rolling
5	Delayed by more than 1 wk	Partial ^b	Slightly reduced	51–75	Mostly half-filled	Full to tight
7	Delayed by more than 2 wks	Half-exserted	Reduced by half	11–50	Half-filled to empty	Tight
9	No heading until soil moisture is replenished	Half-exserted	Reduced by half	0–10	Mostly empty	Tight

^aLate varieties usually recover and produce grains when the rains set in before the end of the test. Reproductive scores are usually less reliable for the late-maturing varieties when rainfall is frequent before the dry season ends. ^bExcept for inherent agronomic traits.

Table 3. Scoring system for recovery (scores taken 1 or 2 days after rewatering).

Decimal scale	Description
1	90% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 1-2 days after watering (or a rain)
3	75% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 1-2 days after watering
5	75-90% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 3-4 days after watering
7	50-75% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 4-5 days after watering
9	Fewer than 50% of plants produce new leaves or tillers 1 week after watering

tems that provide separate criteria for different variety groups, for responses at the vegetative and reproductive stages, and for recovery after rain (Tables 1, 2, 3). Our system should supplement the brief scales given in the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Studies on *Claviceps oryzae sativae*, the incitant of false smut of rice

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Nutritional studies of the fungus *Claviceps oryzae sativae* showed that growth was maximum on yeast peptone potato dextrose agar, followed by that on oatmeal yeast extract, rice yeast dextrose, yeast extract, rice polish, Richard's, Lilly and Barnett's, Raulin's, Coon's, Leonian, Brown's and Czapek's agar. Seven carbon sources were tested. Growth was maximum on maltose followed by mannitol, galactose, starch, sucrose, lactose, and sorbose, and control. Among the nitrogen sources evaluated, asparagine supported maximum growth of the fungus followed by ammonium oxalate, ammonium chlo-

ride, potassium nitrate, peptone, control, sodium nitrate, and tris (hydroxymethyl) methylamine.

Eight isolates of the fungus collected from different parts of India were grouped into four strains on the basis of morphological and cultural characters. A cytological study of the germinating conidium indicated that mitotic division and germ tube formation occur simultaneously. Subsequent nuclear divisions occur quickly to meet the requirement of secondary conidia produced at the rate of 1 nucleus/conidium.

Survival studies of conidia, pseudosclerotia, and true sclerotia showed that the first two propagules do not survive for long either at room temperature or in the field and probably do not serve as the source of primary inoculum in northern India. However, true sclerotia survived sufficiently long at room temperature and in the field and probably act as the primary inoculum source.

Fungicidal evaluation in vitro showed

that Du-Ter, TCMTB, Brestanol, Aureofungin, and Difolatan were effective against the pathogen. Alkaloids were detected in both pseudosclerotia and true sclerotia, which gave positive test for a carbohydrate, glycolipid and for an unsaturated compound, but they differed on the basis of the presence or absence of aldehyde or ketones, or both. ■

Mechanical separation of paddy seeds as applied to plant pathology

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Two major plant pathological constraints in rice production in the Kuttanad tract of Kerala, India, are sheath blight *Corticium sasakii* and sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae*. Sheath rot is relatively new and is difficult to control through chemical means because it is seedborne.

Seed treatment with fungicides